

LANDSAT 7 ETM+

ENHANCING EARTH OBSERVATION AND ENVIRONMENTAL
MONITORING

By

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ABSTRACT

This assignment delves into the comprehensive utility of Landsat 7 Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+) data in the realm of Earth observation and resource management. Landsat 7, a stalwart satellite in the Landsat program, provides a wealth of multispectral imagery crucial for monitoring and analyzing changes in land cover, land use, and natural features. The study highlights the pivotal role of Landsat 7 in diverse applications, including but not limited to agriculture, forestry, disaster management, environmental monitoring, scientific research, and global land use planning. By examining the historical data archive of Landsat 7, the assignment seeks to showcase its enduring significance in contributing to long-term studies, trend analysis, and retrospective assessments. Additionally, it addresses the challenges posed by the scan line corrector issue in 2003 and underscores the continued relevance of Landsat 7 in the context of its technological advancements and subsequent contributions to the understanding of Earth's dynamic landscape. Through this exploration, the assignment aims to underscore the enduring value of Landsat 7 ETM+ data in advancing our understanding of Earth's surface and informing sustainable resource management practices.

KEYWORDS: Landsat 7, Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+), Earth observation, Resource management, Multispectral imagery, Land cover, Land use, Natural features, Agriculture, Forestry, Disaster management, Environmental monitoring, Scientific research.

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© Overview of LANDSAT-7 Mission

Mission Type	:	Earth Imaging
Operator	:	USGS/NASA
Launch Date	:	15 April 1999 18:32:00 UTC
Launch Site	:	Vandenberg SLC-2W
Rocket	:	Delta II 7920
Contractor	:	Boeing
Reference System	:	Geocentric
Inclination	:	98.21degrees
Period	:	98.83minutes
Repeat Interval	:	16days
Altitude	:	705kilometres +/- 5km
Weight	:	1973kg
Mission Duration	:	Elapsed 24 years 6 months and 26 days

© LANDSAT 7 Scientist Team

1. **Darrel Williams:** Project Scientist
2. **James Irons:** Deputy Project Scientist
3. **Jeffrey Masek:** Deputy Team Leader
4. **Dr. Robert Bindshadler:** Instrumental in the creation of the Landsat Image Mosaic of Antarctica (LIMA)
5. **Dr. Samuel N. Goward:** Satellite Mission
6. **Robert Cahalan:** Clear Sky and Cloud-Characterization and Correction for Landsat
7. **Susan Moran:** LANDSAT TM and ETM+ Sata for Resource Monitoring and Management
8. **Luke Flynn :** Analysis of Volcanic Eruptions and Fires Using Landsat
9. **Alexander Goetz:** Land and Land Use
10. **Kurtis J. Thome:** Absolute Radiometric Calibration and Atmospheric Correction of Landsat-7 Thematic Mapper
11. **John R. Schott:** Absolute Calibration and Atmospheric Correction and Application of LANDSAT ETM+ Thermal Infrared Data
12. **David L. Skole:** Acquisition and Analysis of Large Quantities of Landsat 7 Data for measuring Tropical Land Cover Change

1. History of LANDSAT Program

In 1965, William T. Pecora, the then director of the United States Geological Survey, proposed the idea of a remote sensing satellite program to gather facts about the natural resources of our planet. Pecora stated that the program was "*conceived in 1966 largely as a direct result of the demonstrated utility of the Mercury and Gemini orbital photography to Earth resource studies.*" While weather satellites had been monitoring Earth's atmosphere since 1960 and were largely considered useful, there was no appreciation of terrain data from space until the mid-1960s. So, when Landsat 1 was proposed, it met with intense opposition from the Bureau of Budget and those who argued high-altitude aircraft would be the fiscally responsible choice for Earth remote sensing. Concurrently, the Department of Defense feared that a civilian program such as Landsat would compromise the secrecy of their reconnaissance missions. Additionally, there were geopolitical concerns about photographing foreign countries without permission. In 1965, NASA began methodical investigations of Earth remote sensing using instruments mounted on planes. In 1966, the USGS convinced the Secretary of the Interior, Stewart Udall, to announce that the Department of the Interior (DOI) was going to proceed with its own Earth-observing satellite program. This savvy political stunt coerced NASA to expedite the building of Landsat. But budgetary constraints and sensor disagreements between application agencies (notably the Department of Agriculture and DOI) again stymied the satellite construction process. Finally, by 1970 NASA had a green light to build a satellite. Remarkably, within only two years, Landsat 1 was launched, heralding a new age of remote sensing of land from space.

The Hughes Aircraft Company from Santa Barbara Research Center initiated, designed, and fabricated the first three Multispectral Scanners (MSS) in 1969. The first MSS prototype, designed by Virginia Norwood, was completed within nine months, in the fall of 1970. It was tested by scanning Half Dome at Yosemite National Park. For this design work Norwood was called "*The Mother of Landsat*".

Working at NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center, Valerie L. Thomas managed the development of early Landsat image processing software systems and became the resident expert on the Computer Compatible Tapes, or CCTs, that were used to store early Landsat imagery. Thomas was one of the image processing specialists who facilitated the ambitious Large Area Crop Inventory Experiment, known as LACIE — a project that showed for the first time that global crop monitoring could be done with Landsat satellite imagery. The program was initially called the Earth Resources Technology Satellites Program, which was used from 1966 to 1975. In 1975, the name was changed to Landsat. In 1979, President of the United States Jimmy Carter's Presidential Directive 54 transferred Landsat operations from NASA to National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), recommended development of a long term operational system with four additional satellites beyond Landsat 3, and recommended transition to private sector operation of Landsat. This occurred in 1985 when the Earth Observation Satellite Company (EOSAT), a partnership of Hughes Aircraft Company and RCA, was selected by NOAA to operate the Landsat system with a ten-year

contract. EOSAT operated Landsat 4 and Landsat 5, had exclusive rights to market Landsat data, and was to build Landsats 6 and 7.

In 1989, this transition had not been fully completed when NOAA's funding for the Landsat program was due to run out (NOAA had not requested any funding, and U.S. Congress had appropriated only six months of funding for the fiscal year) and NOAA directed that Landsat 4 and Landsat 5 be shut down. The head of the newly formed National Space Council, Vice President Dan Quayle, noted the situation and arranged emergency funding that allowed the program to continue with the data archives intact.

Again in 1990 and 1991, Congress provided only half of the year's funding to NOAA, requesting that agencies that used Landsat data provide the funding for the other six months of the upcoming year. In 1992, various efforts were made to procure funding for follow on Landsats and continued operations, but by the end of the year EOSAT ceased processing Landsat data. Landsat 6 was finally launched on 5 October 1993, but was lost in a launch failure. Processing of Landsat 4 and 5 data was resumed by EOSAT in 1994. NASA finally launched Landsat 7 on 15 April 1999. The value of the Landsat program was recognized by Congress in October 1992 when it passed the Land Remote Sensing Policy Act (Public Law 102-555) authorizing the procurement of Landsat 7 and assuring the continued availability of Landsat digital data and images, at the lowest possible cost, to traditional and new users of the data.

2. Introduction to LANDSAT 7

Landsat 7, launched by NASA in 1999, marked a significant milestone in the history of remote sensing and Earth observation. This assignment provides an overview of Landsat 7, its key specifications, capabilities, mission objectives, and its impact on various applications, including environmental monitoring, land management, and scientific research. Landsat 7 is the seventh satellite of the Landsat program. Launched on 15 April 1999, Landsat 7's primary goal is to refresh the global archive of satellite photos, providing up-to-date and cloud-free images. The Landsat program is managed and operated by the United States Geological Survey, and data from Landsat 7 is collected and distributed by the USGS. The NASA WorldWind project allows 3D images from Landsat 7 and other sources to be freely navigated and viewed from any angle. The satellite's companion, Earth Observing-1, trailed by one minute and followed the same orbital characteristics, but in 2011 its fuel was depleted and EO-1's orbit began to degrade. Landsat 7 was built by Lockheed Martin Space Systems.

In 2016, NASA announced plans to attempt the first ever refueling of a live satellite by refueling Landsat 7 in 2020 with the OSAM-1 mission; as of 2021, the launch date has slipped to 2025.

3. Objectives of LANDSAT Mission

Landsat 7 was launched with specific mission objectives that include:

- Continuation of the Landsat program's legacy in monitoring land surface changes and natural resources.
- Providing data for land cover mapping, land use planning, and resource management.
- Supporting disaster management, environmental studies, and scientific research.

Earth resources, land surface, environmental monitoring, agriculture and forestry, disaster monitoring and assessment, ice and snow cover. 5-year nominal mission life, currently in extended operations with the LST allowed to drift. Routine science mission data operations ended following the declaration of successful Landsat 9 operations. Landsat 7's orbit has been lowered to accommodate a potential OSAM-1 servicing mission in the 2026 timeframe

4. Satellite Specifications

Spectral Bands: The sensor on Landsat 7 captures data in seven spectral bands, spanning the visible, near-infrared, and thermal-infrared regions of the electromagnetic spectrum.

Spatial Resolution: It offers a spatial resolution of 30 meters for most spectral bands, and a 15-meter panchromatic band for higher-resolution imaging.

Radiometric Sensitivity: Landsat 7 provides 8-bit data for most bands, allowing for precise radiometric sensitivity and data interpretation.⁴

5. Spacecraft

The spacecraft and payload were developed under NASA/GSFC management/procurement responsibility (Landsat Project Scientist: D. Williams). The LS-7 satellite was built by LMMS (Lockheed Martin Missiles and Space) at the facility in Valley Forge, PA. The SPACECRAFT features the Landsat-6 bus; an onboard recorder in solid state memory (378 Gbit capacity to capture data beyond the range of ground receiving stations, recording rates of 150 Mbit/s, playback with 300 Mbit/s), and a single observation instrument: ETM+.

The Landsat-7 spacecraft is very similar in design to the Landsat-6 satellite. It features three-axis stabilization with a pointing capability of 180 arcsec (3σ) and a pointing knowledge of 45 arcsec (1σ). Attitude control is provided with four reaction wheels and two torque rods, attitude is sensed with a static Earth sensor, 2 magnetometers and gyros. Orbit control and backup momentum unloading is provided through a blow-down monopropellant hydrazine system with a single tank containing 122 kg of hydrazine.

Figure 1: Illustration of the Landsat-7 spacecraft (image credit: NASA)

Spacecraft mass = 2200 kg, dimensions: 4.3 m in length and 2.8 m in diameter, power = 1550 W [about 1000 W average, provided by a silicon cell solar array (4 panels each of size 1.88 m x 2.26 m) and two nickel hydrogen batteries each of 50 Ahr capacity]. SPACECRAFT design life = 7 years.

The onboard processor performs autonomously executed functions for wideband communications, electrical power management, and satellite control. These include attitude control, redundancy management, antenna steering, battery management, solar array pointing maintenance, thermal profile maintenance, and stored command execution.

RF communications: All data communication is CCSDS compliant. An onboard SSR (Solid State Recorder) is used to capture wideband data from the ETM+ (storage capacity of 378 Gbit, equivalent for about 100 scenes or 42 minutes of instrument data).

- S-band (2 omni-directional antennas), 5 W, for TT&C data with real-time telemetry data rates of 1.2 kbit/s and 4.8

Figure 2: Photo of the Landsat-7 spacecraft during pre-launch activities (image credit: NASA)

kbit/s, and 256 kbit/s of playback data, 2 kbit/s of command data. S-band frequencies of 2106.4 MHz (uplink) and 2287.5 MHz (downlink). The zenith antenna is used for TDRS (Tracking Data and Relay Satellite) communications; the nadir antenna is used for Landsat Ground Network (LGN) communications. Each antenna provides essentially hemispherical coverage.

- X-band (3 steerable antennas), 3.5 W; each antenna transmits data on two channels, with each channel carrying 75 Mbit/s (total of 150 Mbit/s per antenna); up to three separate links are supported. X-band frequencies: 8082.5 MHz, 8212.5 MHz, 8342.5 MHz. The downlink beam width of each antenna is 1.2°.

Ground sites exist at Sioux Falls, South Dakota (Landsat Ground Station, or LGS), Poker Flat, Alaska (Alaska Ground Station, or AGS), Wallops Virginia (WPS), and Svalbard, Norway (SGS). All ground sites are equipped with 11 meter antennas. AGS, SGS, and LGS are capable of receiving both S-band (TT&C) at a downlink rate of 4 kbit/s and X-band (payload) data simultaneously.

Figure 3: Artist's view of the Landsat-7 satellite (image credit: NASA, USGS)

6. Launch

A launch of Landsat-7 took place on a Delta 2 vehicle from VAFB, CA on April 15, 1999.

Orbit: Sun-synchronous polar orbit (AM orbit), altitude = 705 km, inclination = 98.2°, period = 99 minutes, repeat coverage = 16 days, the nominal descending equator crossing time is at 10:00 to 10:15 hours. The ground track is referenced to WRS (Worldwide Reference System) with a repeat accuracy of ± 5 km. The WRS indexes orbits (paths) and scene centers (rows) into a global grid system (daytime and night time) comprising 233 paths by 248 rows. 4)

As of early 2001 Landsat-7 is flying in the so-called “morning constellation,” also referred to as morning train with EO-1 (a few minutes apart), SAC-C and Terra. The objective is to compare coincident imagery from the ETM+ and ALI instruments. The “paired scene” images are used to evaluate the performance of ALI. In fact, the EO-1 and SAC-C spacecraft joined the constellation already on Nov. 21, 2000. The overall objective is to obtain synergistic effects for data interpretation and analysis.

Figure 4: Original morning constellation configuration (image credit: NASA)

7. Sensor Complement

ETM+ (Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus)

ETM+ was built by Raytheon SBRS (Santa Barbara Remote Sensing), Goleta, CA. ETM+ is an 8-band whiskbroom scanning radiometer consisting of:

- A primary mirror that sweeps side-to-side (cross-track) to produce forward and reverse image scans, and
- A scan line corrector (SLC) mirror assembly that sweeps forward-to-aft to compensate for the forward motion of the spacecraft during integration time. The motion of these mirrors deviates from an ideal line profile, introducing along- and cross-track geometric distortions that require compensation.

The principal functional differences between the ETM and the former TM series are the addition of a 15 m resolution panchromatic band and two 8-bit “gain” ranges. The ETM+ adds a 60 m resolution thermal band, replacing the 120 m band on ETM/TM (band No. 6). Design life = 7 years.

Figure 5: ETM+ block diagram (image credit: SBRS)

Figure 6: Schematic of the ETM+ optics subsystem (image credit: NASA)

The Scan Mirror Assembly (SMA) provides the cross-track scanning motion to develop the 185 km long scene swath. The SMA consists of a flat mirror supported by flex pivots on each side (which have compensators to equalize pivot reaction torque), a torquer, a scan angle monitor (SAM), 2 leaf spring bumpers and scan mirror electronics (SME). The bi-directional SMA sweeps the detector's line of sight in west-to-east and east-to-west directions in cross-track direction, while the spacecraft's orbital path provides the north-south motion.

The ETM+ scanner contains 2 focal planes that collect, filter, and detect the scene radiation in a swath, 185 km wide. The primary focal plane consists of optical filters, detectors, and preamplifiers for 5 of the 8 ETM+ spectral bands (bands 1-4, 8). The second focal plane is the cold focal plane which includes the optical filters, infrared detectors, and input stages for ETM+ spectral bands 5,6, and 7. The temperature of the cold focal plane is maintained at 91 K using a radiative cooler. The detector line arrays (16 for VNIR bands, 32 for PAN, and 8 detectors for TIR) of the whiskbroom scanner are oriented in the along-track direction. This arrangement provides a parallel coverage of 480 m along-track in one scan sweep (cross-track direction). The wide along-track coverage permits sufficient integration time for all cells in each scan sweep.

8. LANDSAT-7 ETM+ Bandwidth Specifications

Band No.	Wavelength (µm)	Detectors	IFOV (µrad)	GSD (m)	SNR (at min signal radiance)
8 PAN	0.52 - 0.90	SiPD (32)	18.5 x 21.3	13 x 15	15
1 VIS	0.45 - 0.52	SiPD (16)	42.5	30 x 30	32
2 VIS	0.53 - 0.61	SiPD (16)	42.5	30	35
3 VNIR	0.63 - 0.69	SiPD (16)	42.5	30	26
4 VNIR	0.78 - 0.90	SiPD (16)	42.5	30	32
5 SWIR	1.55 - 1.75	InSb (16)	42.5	30	25
7 SWIR	2.09 - 2.35	InSb (16)	42.5	30	17
6 TIR	10.4 - 12.5	HgCdTe (8)	85.2	60	0.5 K

The ETM+ also includes a number of radiometric enhancements to achieve an absolute radiometric uncertainty of <5% (bands 1-4). Two new calibration devices were added: FAC (Full Aperture Calibrator), and PAC (Partial Aperture Calibrator). ETM+ uses three independent onboard calibration systems (plus preflight calibration), representing a significant step forward in absolute radiometric calibration accuracy. 6) 7)

- A full-aperture solar diffuser (FASC) on the inner surface of the aperture door that illuminates the focal planes with diffusely reflected solar energy when commanded into position
- A partial-aperture solar reflector (PASC) that illuminates the focal planes with attenuated solar energy, once per orbit
- Internal calibrator (IC). Calibration lamps that project calibrated energy onto the focal planes via the main calibration shutter, once per scan, during the scan mirror turnaround.

From the initiation of the LS-7 system, greater attention was paid toward the long-term characterization and calibration of the data than for earlier LS missions. In particular, an IAS (Image Assessment System) was incorporated into the ground processing system. The objective of IAS is to characterize and calibrate the instrument data over the life of the mission.

Figure 7: Cutaway illustration of the ETM+ instrument (image credit: SBRS)

9. Satellite Imagery

In August 1998, NASA contracted EarthSat to produce Landsat GeoCover (Geocover 2000 in NASA WorldWind) — a positionally accurate orthorectified Landsat Thematic Mapper and Multispectral Scanner imagery covering the majority of the Earth's land mass. The contract was part of the NASA Scientific Data Purchase which was administrated through NASA's John C. Stennis Space Center. GeoCover was later enhanced to EarthSat NaturalVue, a simulated natural color Landsat 7 derived circa year 2000, orthorectified, mosaicked and color balanced digital image dataset. Other commercial simulated true color 15-metre global imagery products built from the NASA Landsat 7 imagery include TerraColor from Earthstar Geographics, TruEarth (found in Google Earth and Google Maps) from TerraMetrics, BrightEarth from ComputaMaps, simulated natural color from Atlogis and a product of i-cubed used in NASA WorldWind.

Figure 8: False colour IR image of Washington, D.C., taken by Landsat 7

Large parts of the Earth surface displayed on web mapping services like Google Maps / Google Earth, MSN Maps or Yahoo! Maps are based on enhanced and color balanced Landsat 7 imagery.

10. Benefits of LANDSAT 7

Here are some benefits associated with Landsat 7:

- ❖ **Earth Observation and Monitoring:** Landsat 7 provides high-resolution, multispectral imagery of the Earth's surface. This information is valuable for monitoring changes in land cover, land use, and natural features over time. This capability is crucial for various applications, including agriculture, forestry, urban planning, and environmental management.
- ❖ **Natural Resource Management:** Landsat 7 data is widely used for managing natural resources. It helps in monitoring forests, tracking changes in agricultural land, and assessing water resources. This information is essential for sustainable resource management and conservation efforts.
- ❖ **Disaster Management:** Landsat 7 plays a crucial role in disaster management by providing timely and accurate satellite imagery for assessing the impact of natural disasters such as floods, wildfires, and earthquakes. This information is vital for planning and coordinating disaster response and recovery efforts.
- ❖ **Environmental Monitoring:** Landsat 7 contributes to environmental monitoring by providing data for studying and understanding various environmental processes. Researchers use Landsat data to analyze changes in ecosystems, study climate patterns, and assess the impact of human activities on the environment.
- ❖ **Scientific Research:** Landsat 7 data is valuable for scientific research in fields such as geology, geography, and climatology. Researchers use the satellite imagery to study geological features, landform changes, and atmospheric conditions.
- ❖ **Land Use Planning:** Landsat 7 imagery is utilized in land use planning and management. It provides valuable information for decision-makers to plan urban development, infrastructure projects, and other land-related activities.
- ❖ **Global Coverage:** Landsat 7, along with other satellites in the Landsat program, provides global coverage. This widespread coverage allows for a comprehensive view of Earth's surface, enabling researchers and policymakers to study and address issues on a global scale.
- ❖ **Historical Data Archive:** Landsat 7 has been operational for an extended period, contributing to a significant historical archive of Earth observation data. This archive is useful for long-term studies, trend analysis, and retrospective assessments of changes in the Earth's landscape.

While Landsat 7 has been a valuable asset, it's important to note that it faced a technical issue with its scan line corrector in 2003, which resulted in the acquisition of data with gaps.

Despite this limitation, Landsat 7 has continued to contribute valuable information, and its successor, Landsat 8, has further improved upon its capabilities.

11. Conclusion

Landsat 7 ETM+ has been a cornerstone in the field of remote sensing and environmental monitoring. Its capabilities, advancements, and wide range of applications have made it an invaluable tool for scientists, researchers, and policymakers working to better understand and manage our planet's resources and environment. The sensor's legacy continues to influence the development of future earth observation technologies and the expansion of knowledge in the field of environmental science. Landsat 7 has played a pivotal role in advancing our understanding of Earth's surface dynamics, environmental changes, and resource management. Its enduring legacy is reflected in the continuous improvement of Earth observation technology and the expanding scope of applications in fields such as agriculture, forestry, urban planning, disaster management, and environmental science.

The mission's data accessibility and commitment to open science have fostered a global community of researchers and users, ensuring that Landsat 7's impact endures and continues to shape the future of remote sensing and Earth observation.

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